

ALTERNATIVE TO THE EXISTING METHOD OF DETERMINATION PARAMETERS OF THE ELECTRICAL CIRCUIT FOR TESTING DEVICES FOR ULTIMATE SWITCHING CAPACITY

A. Kobozev

Candidate of Technical Sciences

I. Smilyansky

Candidate of Technical Sciences

Abstract

At present, there is a method for determining the parameters of an electrical circuit for testing devices for maximum switching capacity by processing oscillograms of changes in time of phase currents. This method provides for the need for the operator to perform graphic operations on oscillograms to determine the power factor. It is necessary to draw two envelope lines along the amplitude values of the phase current and draw the average between them by envelopes line. Along the middle line, the values of the constant components of the current necessary for the calculation are determined. $\cos\varphi$. Since the nature of the change in time of phase currents depends on the time of the current occurrence in the circuit, there is an ambiguity in the results of calculating the values of the circuit parameters. The error in measuring the circuit parameters also arises from the different qualifications of the operator when processing oscillograms.

Taking into account the above analysis of the existing method, an alternative method for determining the parameters of the circuit has been developed, in which the conditions and results of the calculation of the parameters do not depend on the moment of current occurrence in the circuit. In addition, the developed method does not provide for any participation of personnel in the process of calculating the parameters - the calculation is carried out according to a simple algorithm by a microprocessor device.

From a scientific point of view, the proposed method is based on the analysis not of the dependence of the change in time of the phase current, but of two other dependencies of the change in time, the nature of which does not depend on the moment of occurrence of the disturbance of the circuit. The peculiarities of the nature of these functions make it possible to determine the value of the current from discrete power values measured 5 and 15 ms after the occurrence of the current $\cos\varphi$. And from the value of the force function measured 16 ms after the occurrence of the current, it is possible to determine the effective value of the phase current.

The peculiarities of the nature of these functions make it possible to determine the value of $\cos\varphi$. And by the value of the force function, measured 16 ms after the current originated, determine the effective value of the phase current.

Keywords: ultimate switching capacity, test circuit, power factor, force function, power.

1. Introduction

Problem Status for Determining the Parameters of the Electrical Circuit for Testing Apparatus

At present, the regulatory documents, for example, in [1], present a method for determining the parameters of an electrical circuit for testing devices for the Ultimate Short-Circuit Breaking Capacity (I_{cu}), based on the analysis of phase current changes. This method is implemented by taking an oscillogram of the change of currents in the phases $i_a = f(t)$, $i_b = f(t)$ and $i_c = f(t)$. The effective value of the current is determined by oscillograms after the attenuation of the aperiodic component of the current. The value of the power factor ($\cos\varphi$) is determined by the degree of attenuation of the aperiodic component of the current. For this purpose, the values of the constant components of the current are determined on the oscillogram, determined by the curve passing in the middle between the envelopes of the amplitudes of the current. In this case, the operator must choose for calculations the phase where the aperiodic component of the current, in his opinion, is the largest. The nature of the dependence in time of the current in the phase depends on the moment of current origination. This means that the error in measuring the value $\cos\varphi$ due to the dependence both on the moment of current occurrence and on the qualification of the operator can be quite significant. Taking into account the analysis of the existing method for calculating the parameters of

the circuit, which we will conventionally call classical, it seems quite urgent to develop a new alternative method. In the new method, there should be no negative impact on the quality of parameter calculations both depending on the moment of current occurrence and the qualification of the operator.

Therefore, the purpose of the work, the results of which are presented in this article, is to develop a method alternative to the classical one, in which graphic and other operator operations are not required to determine the parameters of the test circuit for testing devices for switching capacity, which shall not depend on the moment of disturbance of the electrical circuit. At the same time, the nature of these dependencies must depend significantly on the value of the power factor ($\cos\varphi$). For this, it is necessary that in the steady-state mode the values of these dependencies must be constant. Such a requirement, for example, corresponds to the dependence of the change in time of direct current. Therefore, the nature of the change in direct current in the transient mode depends only on the value of the time constant. But the nature of the change in the value of the alternating current over time does not meet the above requirement.

However, this does not mean that for AC circuits there are no other parameters and their dependencies of changes in time that meet the requirements that ensure

independence from the moment of the circuit disturbance. To determine what these functions are, it is necessary to consider the entire system of generation and transmission of three-phase current as a whole. In this system, the constant in value is the force on the shaft of the generator and its power. These two parameters, which are constant in magnitude over time, are then divided into three variable magnitude constituents.. But in the receiver, the sum of forces and powers will be constant values. This means that the total active power of all three phases and the function characterizing the change in time of the sum of the forces in all three phases (proportional to the square of the values of the currents) will be constant in the steady-state mode. $p(t)$. For the convenience of further presentation, the last dependence is designated as the force function of the electric circuit $-F(t)$.

Taking into account the above analysis, the goal of this work is to develop and substantiate a method for determining the parameters of the test circuit, free from the shortcomings of the classical approach and suitable for full automation based on microprocessor facilities.

2. Theoretical foundations of an alternative method for determining the parameters of the test network

An alternative method for determining the parameters of the test circuit is based on the peculiarities of the nature of the active power of the network and its force function in the transient mode.

2.1 Characteristics of the Time-Varying Nature of Total instantaneous Power.

The instantaneous power of a single-phase electric circuit connected to an inductive load is described by the following expression:

$$p(t) = U_m \sin(\omega t + \psi) \cdot I_m [\sin(\omega t + \psi - \varphi) - \sin(\psi - \varphi) e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}] \quad (1)$$

where U_m and I_m — are the amplitude values of the phase voltage and current; ψ — is the random initial phase of the voltage, characterizing the instant at which the disturbance occurs; φ — is the system phase angle of the circuit; and τ — is the electromagnetic time

constant of the electrical circuit, related to the angle φ by the expression $\omega\tau = \text{tg}\varphi$.

The formula for the total instantaneous power of a three-phase system can be written as follows:

$$P(t) = \sum_{k=0}^2 U_m \sin(\omega t + \psi - k2\pi/3) \cdot I_m [\sin(\omega t + \psi - k2\pi/3 - \varphi) - \sin(\psi - k2\pi/3 - \varphi) e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}] \quad (2)$$

The time variation of the total instantaneous power of the three phases, $P(t)$ —following simple yet rather cumbersome transformations—is described by the following expression:

$$p(t) = 1.5 U_m I_m [\cos(\varphi) - \cos(\omega t + \varphi) e^{-t/\tau}] \quad (3)$$

An analysis of expression (3) reveals that the behavior of the function $p(t)$ from the onset of the transient process, takes the form of damped oscillations relative to the steady-state value. It should be noted that expression (3) contains no components with a frequency of $f = 2\omega$, as these mutually cancel out within the total power. This result of the analytical analysis is corroborated by extensive computer simulations, as well as by experiments conducted to determine the of power variation during the startup of a 15 kW electric motor.

An investigation into the extrema of relationship (3) with respect to t demonstrated that all points at which extrema occur for the function $p(t)$ are independent of the values of $\cos \varphi$ —that is of τ , and are determined by the following expression:

$$\omega t_e = \pi/2 + (n-1)\pi \quad (4)$$

where odd values of n correspond to the maxima P_{max} , and even values n - to the minima of the total instantaneous power, P_{min} .

For circuits with varying current at $f = 50$ Hz, the first maximum occurs at time $t = \pi/(2\omega) = 0.005$ s, while the first minimum occurs at $t = 3\pi/(2\omega) = 0.015$ s. It is quite evident that if a different mains frequency is applied—for example, $f = 60$ Hz, the temporal parameters will differ.

Figure 1 illustrates the $p(t)$ dependencies, plotted in accordance with expression (1), for $\cos\varphi$ values ranging from 0.2 to 0.7 .

Рис.1 Зависимость $p=f(t)$ при разных значениях $\cos\varphi$

As is evident from the provided graphs, the maximum values of the total instantaneous power P_5 vary only slightly by 2–4%, as $\cos\varphi$ changes, whereas the minimum values P_{15} differ significantly. As the analysis demonstrated, it is advisable to select as the criterion

for determining $\cos\varphi$ not the direct ratio of the extreme power values, but rather the ratio of their difference to their sum, expressed by the coefficient K_p :

$$K_p = \frac{P_5 - P_{15}}{P_5 + P_{15}} \quad (5)$$

Рис.2 Зависимость $\cos\varphi$ от K_p

Fig. 2 illustrates the relationship between $\cos\varphi$ and the coefficient K_p . The range of $\cos\varphi$ values corresponds to the range of $\cos\varphi$ values (0.2–0.7) for test circuits required by regulatory documentation [2].

By utilizing the derived relationship $\cos\varphi=f(K_p)$, the power factor $\cos\varphi$ can be determined based on two power values measured 5 ms and 15 ms after current inception in the test circuit.

The advantage of the proposed method for determining the power factor ($\cos\varphi$)—which is based on power analysis—lies in the fact that the value of $\cos\varphi$ can be easily determined using just two "reference" points, P_5 and P_{15} , from the $p(t)$ curve. Specifically, it is necessary to record the instantaneous power values P_5 and P_{15} at 5 ms and 15 ms after the current onset; subsequently, the value of K_p is calculated using Formula (5), and the value of $\cos\varphi$ is then determined based on the data presented in the graph in Fig. 2. Notably, this approach eliminates the need to employ an

operator to perform manual graphical constructions—a requirement inherent to the implementation of the classical method.

2.2 Features of the nature of changes in the force function over time

In general, the force function is defined by the following expression:

$$F_s(t) = [i_a(t)]^2 + [i_b(t)]^2 + [i_c(t)]^2 \quad (6)$$

where $i_a(t)$, $i_b(t)$ and $i_c(t)$ are the dependencies of the change in time of phase currents.

After substituting the known expressions of the time change of phase currents, the expression for the force function takes the following form:

$$F_s(t) = 3I_f^2(1 - 2e^{-t/\tau} \cos \omega t + e^{-2t/\tau}) \quad (7),$$

where τ is the electromagnetic time constant, I_f - is the effective value of the phase

Fig.3 Graphs of the force function at different $\cos\varphi$ values

The main feature of the force function is the independence of its character from the time of the occurrence of the disturbance current. Therefore, the

character of the force function $F_s(t)$ depends only on the time constant τ or the power factor $\cos\varphi$. Experimental verification of the nature of the force

function was carried out [6] in circuits with short-circuit currents of the order of 45 kA. Fig.3 shows graphs of the force function at different values $\cos\varphi$.

Let us consider other features of the nature of the force function. If we analyze the expression (6) for the force function $F_s(t)$ by the extremum, then as a result

we get the following expression for the pronounced value dF_s/dt :

$$(\cos\omega t_{max}-\varphi)-\cos\varphi e^{-\frac{t_{max}}{\tau}}=0 \quad (8)$$

where t_{max} - is the time for the force function to reach its maximum value F_{max} .

Fig.4 Dependence of time t_{max} on value $\cos\varphi$

A similar expression is obtained for the derivative of the phase current dt in which the shock current occurred I_y due to the fact that the circuit disturbances occurred at the time of the passage of the EMF of this phase through zero. From the equality of expressions for species, it follows that the moment of time when the function $F_s(t)$ reaches its maximum value F_{max} at the same time at which the shock current I_y would arise in one of the phases. Fig.4 shows the dependence of time t_{max} on the value $\cos\varphi$ - $t_{max} = f(\cos\varphi)$, obtained by the numerical solution of equation (8).

Let us continue the analysis of the nature of the force function. If we consider that the impact coefficient of the chain K_y is expressed by the following equation $K_y = I_y/I_f$, then the expression (7) for $F_s(t)$ will be as follows:

$$F_s(t) = 3I_y^2 \frac{1-2e^{-t/\tau} \cos \omega t + e^{-2t/\tau}}{K_y^2} \quad (9)$$

For the case where the instantaneous value of the force function reaches its maximum value, the expression F_{max} will be as follows:

$$F_{max} = 3I_y^2 \frac{1-2e^{-t_{max}/\tau} \cos \omega t_{max} + e^{-2t_{max}/\tau}}{K_y^2} \quad (10)$$

Let's transform the denominator in the expression (10). Let us take into account that the times of reaching the values F_{max} and I_y are the same and equal to t_{max} . Let us also take into account that the expressions for the derivatives of the force function and the phase current with the shock current are the same. After a series of substitutions and transformations, we get the following expression of the denominator dF/dt :

$$1 - 2e^{-t_{max}/\tau} \cos \omega t_{max} + e^{-2t_{max}/\tau} = K_y^2 \quad (11)$$

It follows that expression (10) for the reference point of the force function F_{max} will have the following form:

$$F_{max} = 3I_y^2 \quad (12)$$

The magnitude of the shock current I_y is given by the following expression:

$$I_y = \sqrt{F_{max}/3} \quad (13)$$

Let us continue the analysis of the features of the nature of the force function. As can be seen from Fig.3, the value of the function $F_s(t)$ at the moment of time 16 ms after the occurrence of the disturbance current (the value F_{16}) with a small error is equal to the value proportional to the square of the value of the steady state value of the phase current I_f^2 .

$$F_{16} \sim 3I_f^2 \quad (14)$$

Hence the following expression for determining the value of the effective value of the phase current I_f :

$$I_f = \sqrt{F_{16}/3} \quad (15)$$

Using expressions (12) and (14), the impact coefficient K_y of the circuit can be defined as the ratio of the value of the shock current to the I_y value of the effective value of the phase current I_f :

$$K_y = \sqrt{F_{max}/F_{16}} \quad (16)$$

The advantages of the proposed method for determining the value of the shock current I_y and the effective value of the phase current I_f , based on the analysis of the force function are that by two "reference" points F_{max} and F_{16} it is easy to determine the above values I_y and I_f .

To determine the effective value of the current I_f it is necessary to measure the discrete values of the

phase currents at the time 16 ms after the current originates, square them and add them together. The sum of the squares of the specified phase currents constitutes the second reference point of the force function F_{16} . The effective current value is then calculated using the formula $I_f = \sqrt{F_{16}/3}$.

2.3. *Algorithm for the implementation of an alternative method for determining the parameters of the test circuit by a microprocessor device*

Fig.5 shows the algorithm for the implementation by a microprocessor device of an alternative method for determining the parameters of an electrical circuit for testing on a PCS. The algorithm is represented by 3 modules, which do not physically exist, they combine a number of mathematical operations to calculate a particular parameter of the test circuit

Fig.5 Algorithm for the implementation of an alternative method for determining the parameters of the test circuit

In module 1, instantaneous power values $p = f(t)$ are determined from the incoming information of the total power P_5 and P_{15} at times of time, respectively, 5 ms and 15 P_5 ms after the occurrence of the circuit disturbance. In the same module, the coefficient of P_{15} the ratio of these values is determined from the found values by the expression $K_p = (P_5 - P_{15}) / (P_5 + P_{15})$. In the same module, the value of $\cos\phi$ is determined by the dependence of $\cos\phi = f(K_p)$.

In Module 2 the value t_{max} is determined from the relationship between the time at which the maximum value of the force function occurs t_{max} and the value of $\cos\phi$. In the same module, the instantaneous values of the phase currents i_{amax} , i_{bmax} and i_{cmax} at the time of the -values t_{max} . In the same module, the instantaneous values of the phase currents at time $t = 16$ ms after the time of the occurrence of the circuit disturbance are determined - the values i_{a16} , i_{b16} and i_{c16} .

In modulom 3, the values of currents i_{amax} , i_{bmax} and i_{cmax} are squared and summed up. The sum of these squares of the currents represents the value of the

force function F_{max} . In the same module, the magnitude of the shock current I_y is determined by the expression $I_y = \sqrt{F_{max}/3}$. In the same module, the magnitudes of the currents i_{a16} , i_{b16} and i_{c16} are squared and summed up. The sum of the specified squares of the current values is the value of the line of force F_{16} in the same module determine the effective value of the shock current I_f by the expression $I_f = \sqrt{F_{16}/3}$

Summary

A method for automated determination of the parameters of an electrical circuit has been developed to check the maximum switching capacity of electrical devices. This method is an alternative to the method (classical), which is set out in regulatory documents. The classical method is based on the analysis of an oscillogram with the dependence of the change in time of the current in phase. Due to the fact that the nature of the change in the phase current depends on the time of the current occurrence in the electrical circuit, the initial

conditions for processing oscillograms cannot be constant and the most informative. This affects the value of the error in measuring the circuit parameters. The value of the measurement error is also influenced by the level of qualification of the operator when performing the necessary graphic operations in the process of processing oscillograms. The developed alternative method for determining the parameters of the test circuit is based on the analysis of two dependencies of change in time, the nature of which does not depend on the moment of occurrence of current in the circuit, but essentially depends on the value of the power factor of the circuit ($\cos\varphi$). These dependencies are the time dependence of the total power for the three phases and the force function (the time dependence of the sum of the squares of the instantaneous current values of the three phases). By two reference points for each of these dependencies, it is possible to determine the values of $\cos\varphi$, the shock current of I_y the circuit, and the effective value of the phase current I_f , using a simple algorithm.

The advantages of the developed alternative method for determining the parameters of the test circuit are the uselessness of the operator for graphic processing of oscillograms, the stability of the results of calculations of parameter values and the automated process of calculating parameter values by a microprocessor device.

References

1. GOST 2933-83 (2002). "Low-voltage electric devices. Test methods." <https://stv39.ru/docs/normativnye-dokumenty-po-elektrike/gosty-natsionalnye-standarty.php>
2. GOST R 50030.1-2000. "The distribution and control equipment is low-voltage. Part 1. General requirements and test methods." (IEC 60947-2), <https://stv39.ru/docs/normativnye-dokumenty-po-elektrike/gosty-natsionalnye-standarty.php>
3. V.E. Rainin, A.S. Kobozev, Y.N. Barchenkov "Methods for Determining the Parameters of the Test Circuit for the Automated Process of Testing Electrical Apparatuses", *Elektrotechnica*, 2016, No 7, pp. 58-62